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Publishing a Research: Shared Experiences of Preservice Teachers as Novice Researchers in Research Journals

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Abstract: Publishing research is crucial and is of utmost significance. However, it is a daunting task for most researchers, especially if one is a beginner with very limited experience. The generalizability of much of the previously published research was limited to the negative aspects of the publishing process rather than the whole circumstances they had to face. Therefore, this article sought to explore the experiences of preservice teachers as novice researchers in publishing their research outputs in a research journal. This study employed a qualitative-phenomenological approach. Five major themes emerged from the interview with eight purposively selected former preservice teachers who had first-time encounters in publishing that the research investigates. These themes were encapsulated through the acronym "FLAME," namely: (a) facing personal circumstances, (b) leveraging positive dispositions, (c) acknowledging dependency on research promoter, (d) meeting publishing standards, and (e) encountering poor physical and mental well-being. This article concludes that the journal publishing process is a multidimensional and enriching experience, providing the full spectrum of positive and negative experiences for novice researchers. This paper highlighted some implications that can be used as a guide to support novice researchers in the publication process.

Keywords: *Research experiences, research journal, research publication, undergraduate researchers.*

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Introduction

Publication plays a vital role in the research process as it ensures the dissemination of findings and extends the impact beyond the completion of the study. However, only some have successfully made their work publicly known, provided that inhibitors rise, impeding scholars from doing so (Masango, 2015). It is reported that 62% of papers have been rejected at least once by other journals before publication (Hall & Wilcox, 2007). The grave reasons for rejecting papers are difficulty with research expertise, lack of time, funding, and staff support (Bullen & Reeve, 2011; Dreyer & Peiffer, 2015). Correspondingly, associated with these are ethical expectations mainly, fraudulent behavior, misuse of intellectual property, appropriation, and plagiarism (Babalola et al., 2012). Respectively, whether from local or international institutions, research publication is unequivocally vital because its purpose is to legitimize and authorize an article to be reliable in its target discipline (Hausmann & Murphy, 2016; Pho & Tran, 2016).

An established body of research dealing with publishing from postgraduate schools expounds that publication is a potential determining factor for career advancement (Shelby & Okilwa, 2011). It is a well-known route to success and recognition and an essential path for sharing groundbreaking research in a field (Jasper et al., 2014; Sengupta et al., 2014). However, as a natural successor to research study, it is inclined with predicaments (Tella & Onyancha, 2021). It is given that a deficiency of training in a specific study area is a barrier to research publication (Altikriti, 2022; McClellan et al.,

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2017). However, predatory publishing and fake academic conferences can subject academic papers to irrelevance (Taylor, 2019). In addition, factors that contribute to the struggles of publishing also involve the personal issues of postgraduate researchers, such as poor physical and mental health (Al-Kumaim et al., 2021). Data from several studies revealed that feelings of discomfort and fear of rejection concerning the high expectations of their mentors, as well as commitment issues with their personal life and non-curricular responsibilities, are also barriers for postgraduate researchers to work on their research output (Alvarez et al., 2014; Bocar, 2009). Together, these results prove that it is crucial to strategize family, social obligation, mastering a schedule, focusing on academic writing, and acknowledging authorship (Stoilescu & McDougall, 2010).

Investigating challenges among undergraduate students is a continuing concern within research publications. Most published undergraduate research are found to be concentrated under the med-allied, political science, and other humanities research. It was manifested that the research publication process affects their academic performance and psychological well-being (Alsaleem et al., 2021). It was revealed that they were not encouraged by their seniors and faculty to participate in the research process and undertake research publications due to pressure, prompting fear of falling behind on the portfolio of the students (Griffin & Hindocha, 2011; Mahalingam et al., 2018). As these result in more significant retraction rates from undergraduate students, the publication appears to be closely linked with the call to implement new frameworks and academic resources corroborated to be vital in encouraging students the development of scientific research (Bovijn et al., 2017; Corrales-Reyes & Dorta-Contreras, 2018). Also, many undergraduate researchers are reluctant to engage in an effective and equitable publishing method because of financial burdens placed on them by large for-profit publishers to make research outcomes freely accessible (Siegel et al., 2018). The lack of incentives provided by universities for open research as well as the changes and increasing costs of libraries, are among the conflicts faced by undergraduate researchers (Hampson, 2020). These contribute to time constraints and, unfortunately, the continued marginalization of research (Moahi, 2011). Hence, it is conceivable to hypothesize that the underlying reasons for a study not being subsequently published have more to do with the author, the faculty, and the scholastic institution and the foregoing drawbacks.

The challenges faced by undergraduate students in research publication have been extensively investigated, particularly in the fields of med-allied, political science, and humanities (Alsaleem et al., 2021; Bovijn et al., 2017; Corrales-Reyes & Dorta-Contreras, 2018; Griffin & Hindocha, 2011; Hampson, 2020; Mahalingam et al., 2018; Moahi, 2011; Siegel et al., 2018). These are drawn from studies undertaken in health care colleges in a particular university concerning departments of applied medical science, nursing, dentistry, medicine, and pharmacy, and insufficient were made on non-med allied colleges such as language and education (Alsaleem et al., 2021). Such expositions are unsatisfactory because they focused on the negative aspects of the publishing process, neglecting the full range of supportive and counteractive forces that these researchers encounter (Shah et al., 2009). Due to the lack of research attention, teacher educators have long remained an underexplored research area (Hangul et al., 2022). Thus, it could have been more relevant if a wider range of preservice teachers and novice researchers with limited experience in past publications of had been explored. Preservice teachers are undergraduate students enrolled in teacher training programs and have not started their careers as teachers (Farhadiba & Wulyani, 2020). This extends to the idea of being a novice researcher, often defined as individuals with limited prior experience in research publication (Buabeng-Andoh, 2012). Despite the need to examine their experiences to enhance the understanding of the publication process, this indicates a more profound understanding regarding their experiences in publishing research journals. This study aims to address this gap by shedding light on preservice teachers' experiences as they navigate the publication of their first research works in academic journals. The fundamental question this study seeks to answer is: How do preservice teachers, as novice researchers, experience publishing their research work in a research journal?

This study will impact preservice teachers and researchers by revealing the experiences that new students face when submitting their work to academic journals. Preservice teachers and researchers may be encouraged, knowing they are not alone. It will also impact academic journals by offering specific information on what the researchers face problems, how they overcame the obstacles in their journey, how they improved their research, and others. Moreover, it will provide the unique perspective of preservice teachers, who are novice researchers, on what they learn in and outside the classroom. This study shows how much these individuals have learned as novice researchers and how much they have grown through research. This research will benefit both teacher and student by reducing the struggle and confusion of being a novice researcher.

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed qualitative research to investigate the true-to-life experiences of preservice teachers as novice researchers who published their research in research journals. Qualitative research explores and provides a deeper understanding of real-life experiences in gathering non-numerical data to create a phenomenon hypothesis (Moser & Korstjens, 2017). This specific study utilized the phenomenological approach since it explored the experiences of preservice teachers as novice researchers publishing in a research journal. The phenomenological approach delves into the study of various phenomena, like the different aspects of human social experience, to interpret or formulate objective

descriptions of lived human experiences (Alhazmi & Kaufmann, 2022; Wilson, 2015). Interviews were used to obtain first-hand accounts of the preservice teachers who had first-time encounters in publishing that the research investigated.

Settings and Participants

This study utilized a purposive sampling method to identify its participants. Purposive sampling is obtaining a sample by taking a topic that depends on a particular objective rather than the level or field (Rosa, 2018). It is the planned selection of participants depending on their capacity to elucidate a particular theme, idea, or phenomenon. Purposive sampling in qualitative research is a technique in which a researcher discerns who will participate in the study. Using a purposive sampling method is most helpful in exploring phenomena, topics, or ideas.

In this study, eight (8) participants were subjected and selected based on the set inclusion criteria: (1) only former preservice teachers of the Teacher Education (TE) program in one of the private universities in Northern Luzon; (2) only those who were considered novices in research at the time when their research was published in research journals from the 2016-2022 academic years. Individuals who enter the research field with no or little prior publication experience are classified as novice researchers (Shah et al., 2009).

Instrumentation

To gather data for analysis, a semi-structured in-depth interview was developed. Three educational experts have validated and endorsed the interview protocol, consisting of 10 fundamental questions that address the main question: How do preservice teachers, as novice researchers, experience publishing their research work in a research journal? These questions were asked in either English or Filipino, depending on the participants' language preference, to enable them to convey their thoughts spontaneously. Ergo, this will allay barriers that spawn distrust and fear to express thoughts and ideas.

Table 1. Interview Schedule for the Participants

Type of Question	Sample Interview Question
Opening	How did you perceive the importance of publishing your research work in a research journal for your professional development?
	How did you navigate the process of selecting a suitable research journal for publication?
	What challenges did you, as a preservice teacher, face when attempting to publish your research work in a research journal?
Transitory	How did you validate the data of your research study, considering your limited experience in writing a manuscript for publication?
	What strategies did you employ to overcome barriers and successfully write a research article for submission to a research journal?
Body/Central	How did you handle the peer review process and address the reviewer's comments and suggestions?
	What support or guidance did you receive from your academic mentors about publishing your research work?
Concluding/ Utmost	What emotions or feelings did you experience throughout the publication process, from submission to acceptance?
	What significant opportunities or exposures did you experience after publishing your research in a professional journal?
	What impact did publishing in a research journal have on your confidence and competence as a future educator and researcher?

Data Explication and Analysis

Data were collected using an interview guided by interview questions. A virtual interview was conducted through video conferencing apps and websites, primarily Zoom, Google Meet, and Facebook Messenger video chat.

With permission from the participants, the data were recorded on a digital audio recorder. A comprehensive and coherent interview guide was designed, prepared, reviewed, and secured before the session to ascertain congruous flow. This helped extract critical messages from participants' responses to achieve the research goal. Moreover, necessary and comprehensible follow-up questions were given to clarify ambiguities. Despite a recorded copy of the interview, the interviewers saved the participants' answers on a notepad as a backup in case of unavoidable technical failures.

The interview was conducted during the participants' convenient time. The researcher began with a brief explanation of the research goal, background, and interview format. The interviews began with a short list of guide questions, followed by more in-depth questions based on the interviewee's responses to the semi-structured interviews (DeJonckheere & Vaughn, 2019). An interview lasting, on average, 40 minutes was designed to form a shared understanding between the interviewer and respondent (Husband, 2020).

The sets of data were subjected to coding approaches for analyzing and interpreting. Themes are created using coding and condensing the codes (Creswell, 2007). Assuming the role of analysts, the researchers executed the following process: (1) initial coding, (2) examining and identifying significant words or phrases, called in-vivo codes (Noble & Smith, 2014), (3) analyzing, arranging, and transcribing the gathered data, (4) transferring of recorded data and connecting it with analytical coding (Stuckey, 2014), and (5) performing axial coding to provide a coding framework or template from which to synthesize and organize data into more coherent, hierarchically structured categories and sub-categories that add nuance and dimension to emergent concepts and their potential relationship to other framework elements (Scott & Medaugh, 2017).

Additionally, cool and warm analyses were used to compare and contrast the codes extracted from the collected data. The cool analysis extracts meaningful information from the participants' statements. On the contrary, warm analysis is used to observe and characterize the shared collective phenomena experienced by the participants, highlighting any commonalities in the process (David & Aruta, 2018). A numeric code (e.g., P1, P2, P3, etc.) was assigned to the participants to be interviewed for specification and to protect their privacy.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were involved in every stage of this research as they are viewed as necessary in providing a qualitative study concerning the role of the researcher (Sanjari et al., 2014). Ethical factors include the assurance of confidentiality, choosing the appropriate tool when dealing with sensitive topics, constructing a consent form for the data-gathering procedure, addressing possible risks, and ethically reviewing the research (Dongre & Sankaran, 2016).

The fundamental ethical principle that this study concentrated on is informed consent, which lies at the core of ethical research practice and underpins the design and management of research. This upholds the privacy and security of the participants (Hardicre, 2014). Given the circumstances, the researchers conducted the study in accordance with proper protocols and courtesy by requesting participants' permission to participate in the study in a letter endorsed by the Undergraduate Research and Innovation Coordinator (UGRIC) and the Dean of the School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts (STELA).

The endorsement letter established a clear grasp of the study's purpose and helped the participants comprehend the significance of their involvement. Regardless of whether they affirmed or refused to take part, the viewpoints voiced by the participants were recognized and acknowledged. Confidentiality and anonymity are vital components of ethical research practice. Researchers strived to reassure participants that every possible effort was made to ensure that the data they submit cannot be linked back to them in reports, presentations, and other forms of dissemination (Crow & Wiles, 2008).

On that premise, dispensed accounts and identities were kept confidential and anonymous. In other respects, researchers asked for further green light and permission to record and document the interview, keeping with the Data Privacy Act. If the participants agreed, recorded audio and video files were only made procurable to the researchers' data analysis and interpretation determination. Subsequently, all data collected will be withdrawn after the purpose is fulfilled.

Findings/Results

This study is postulated upon the early procured data on the published challenges and struggles observed by publication editors, experienced by post-graduate and undergraduate students in med-allied, political science, and other humanities courses. After a series of collecting data from the novice researchers of the Teacher Education Program in one of the private institutions in Northern Luzon, the data on the entire experience of the researchers can now be disseminated into dimensions.

Five themes, The Flame Model: Experiences of Novice Researchers in Publishing Research, have emerged. They are as follows: (1) facing personal circumstances, (2) leveraging positive dispositions, (3) acknowledging dependency on research promoter, (4) meeting publishing standards, and (5) encountering poor physical and mental well-being. These themes reveal the interconnectedness of the dimensions.

Figure 1. The FLAME Model: Experiences of Novice Researchers in Publishing Research

The FLAME Model: Experiences of Novice Researchers in Publishing Research indicates the researcher's various experiences that expose the publication process for preservice novice researchers. As a flame, it fuels the motivation of the preservice teachers to publish, to see it not just to advance their professional endeavors but to illuminate and ignite further discoveries in the field of Teacher Education. However, it is also a flame in a way that the challenges the researchers experienced along the way burn and decrease the blaze of their aspirations. However, such demotivating and deplorable encounters are just fragments of the actual flame. Despite all that was given, they had the torch to hold onto: their research promoters and the academe. It helps them with their beginnings, to drive, and best of all, to reach the desired outcome of publication—to expand the horizons of knowledge and discovery. Hence, just like a flame, the experiences of novice researchers enkindled with passion and inspiration, will flare up the publication journey of aspiring publishers.

Facing Personal Circumstances

The first dimension of the FLAME Model focuses on Facing Personal Circumstances where novice researchers experience individually entrenched matters while publishing their first research work. Three components were classified to have influenced the experience of novice researchers, namely, commitment issues, time constraints, and financial burdens.

Commitment issues spring from novice researchers having other priorities and responsibilities while publishing. Some are finishing their undergraduate programs and working already, while others are still undergoing teaching internships or club activities. These commitment matters generated the issue of time constraints. The novice researchers revealed it was time-consuming as other priorities limited their time to work constantly on the publishing process. Relative to the components of commitment issues and time constraints, the novice researchers stated:

“Since I am already working, it is hard to find time to revise.” (P1)

“It was time-consuming because I needed to focus on my studies, and as I am already an irregular student, I needed to be obedient in school.” (P6)

“Since there are a lot of requirements in school, it resulted in having a lack of time and I had problems with my time management.” (P7)

“Since one of us is from Ifugao, I am from Bataan, while the other is from Pangasinan, we tried to consider the mutual places and time as some of us try to adjust schedules. Most likely, we consider the time of each other.” (P8)

Another component of personal circumstances is the financial burdens brought about by the publishing opportunity. The novice researchers identified having to prepare costly expenses in continuing the publication process to ensure the quality of the paper by having to call upon the help of experts. As Participant 6 put it:

“We needed to ensure that our paper was grammatically correct. So, with my expenses, I consulted a language expert to check our research paper.”

Leveraging Positive Dispositions

The second dimension of the FLAME Model is leveraging positive dispositions. Two components build up leveraging positive dispositions of preservice teachers as novice researchers. These components include (1) positive dispositions toward publication experience and (2) seen as a potential determining factor for career advancement.

Regarding the positive dispositions towards publication experience, the novice researchers are rectified with some sense of fulfillment, explore the publication process and worthwhile hard work. It is widely believed that through these positive dispositions, novice researchers know what to expect in publishing and be sure of a potential component for their career advancements as preservice teachers. Some participants hold the view that:

“We were really glad and excited because it was our first time actually in the department, and somehow we managed to publish at least one paper.” (P1)

“It was fulfilling, and then I was happy because I never expected that we would publish our work online.” (P7)

Aside from positive dispositions towards publication experience, preservice teacher participants also regarded research publication as a potential determining factor for career advancement. The preservice teachers cited the research publication as an “opening door for job opportunities. This means that the published research allows preservice teachers to explore new career opportunities for their future endeavors. Parallel to the two components of leveraging positive dispositions of preservice teachers, these participants posited:

“If you are going to apply for a job, they will really look for a publication from you, especially since we are teachers, and that's also like additional points.” (P2)

“The fact that you have published research plays a significant role in giving companies or institutions the idea that you are good at research.” (P8)

Acknowledging Dependency on Research Promoter

The third dimension of novice researchers' FLAME of experiences in publishing research is the dependency on the research promoter. In this study, research promoter is a relative term which means supervisors that provide guidance to ensure that the research project is effectively concluded. This dimension is quite revealing in several ways as these views surfaced mainly with how the researchers, as novice ones, became dependent on their research promoter in the publication process. What stands out in this dimension are the transactions and direct communications made by the research promoter, including the guidance, ways, and intention to publish the paper, which most participants have opined. For instance, novice researchers have mentioned that their research promoter had direct, firsthand communication point-of-contact of the publication. On no account, most novice researchers experienced direct communication with the publication. Participants 1 and 6 propounded:

“All transactions were made and retrained to that of publication, and then my adviser.” (P1)

“To tell you honestly, there was no direct communication between the publication and me. All information goes through my promoter. It was like all information passed to me was already filtered, and all I had to do was to move.” (P6)

A recurrent theme in the interviews was a sense amongst participants that they concede that they are novices in the publishing process. This means that their conception of the publication process is bounded and deficient, thus, necessitating the expertise and guidance of their research promoter. Two of the novice researcher participants expressed:

“It was a go-with-the-flow among the group. Since we have limited experience in publishing, our research promoter guided us throughout the process. Limited in a way that we do not know anything about the process. Seeing that our promoter had beforehand experience in publishing research, most likely, it is the guidance of our promoter.” (P8)

“It was a good thing that our research promoter was there, and she was the one who facilitated us and guided us in editing our research.” (P4)

Further, participants alluded to the notion of their insufficient experience and expertise in publishing. As participants 6 and 7 put it:

“Our research promoter received higher stress than I because he was the direct contact person of the publication.” (P6)

“It is hard to publish if you are on your own. If we do not have the help of the research promoter, we will not finish it smoothly.” (P7)

Moreover, this dimension also emerged in discussions of how novice researchers have pursued publication because of their research promoter's initiative and intention to publish their paper. Some reported that they had no plans to publish their paper, which was just relatively for compliance's sake. While most participants agreed that their research promoter took the initiative to publish their paper, they were encouraged to publish. This view was echoed by participants 3 and 8:

“It was actually our promoter’s main initiative to pursue our publication or the publishing of our journal.” (P3)

“Our research promoter decided to push through the publication because he felt that our study was unique.” (P8)

Meeting Publishing Standards

The fourth dimension of The FLAME Model is meeting publishing standards. Most participants have responded that in the making of their research, certain standards and guidelines have been enforced on them by their promoters and journal publishers. These standards range from their research's format, appropriateness, and correctness. One example of such is the appropriateness of their study in adhering to the readership interest of the journal and the community the study is being conducted. As mentioned by Participant 5:

“As researchers, we were considering our field of specialization, so the journals we considered submitting to were more inclined with our specialization.” (P5)

Included in this process is also checking the legitimacy and reliability of the journal publication that the novice researchers applied for. This code further displays the researcher's experience, ensuring their legitimacy during publication to avoid predatory journals by checking their qualifications. From the statements of participants 2 and 3:

“We have to ensure that the journal is not predatory.” (P2)

“We have to make sure that the publication, the company, or the publisher is legitimate.” (P3)

The adherence to these guidelines would lead them to revise their initial research draft by redacting and adding research sections. This process during the publication is where most of the researchers experienced the most difficulty. From learning highfalutin terminologies and distributing and redistributing papers to hyper-linking references, these lead them to mention that such assignments are challenging:

“I can describe it as strenuous. Going back again to the thing that I have said earlier, there are things that you must consider, and that there are guidelines that you must follow.” (P4)

“It is difficult to understand the terminologies that the publication used. I do not remember exactly the words they used, but they were highfalutin.” (P5)

“It is very challenging because there are a lot of revisions done since it is a professional publication.” (P5)

With the pressure of adhering to foreign standards in an unfamiliar process, the experience of uncertainty from their limited experience in this dimension is a common expression. In the words of Participants 1 and 8:

“We do not have any idea of what the structure of a research article or published research article is.” (P1)

“Since we are limited in a way, we do not know much about the process and what are the things we should consider in publishing.” (P8)

Encountering Poor Physical and Mental Well-Being

The fifth dimension of The FLAME Model refers primarily to their physical and mental well-being; they experience pressures, difficulty, nerve-wracking tediousness, stress, exhaustion, and intimidation as novice researchers in publishing a research journal. Having the thought that their research will be rejected, the preservice teacher, as a novice researcher, feels that their paper is not worth it; in these circumstances, they feel bad about themselves for publishing their research. The novice researchers feel overwhelmed by research publications. The expectation of novice researchers that their research would be rejected was when they wondered if their research study would qualify for publication.

“It was tedious, and then it was very detailed.” (P3)

“Publishing the research was nerve-wracking, and it became more challenging.” (P4)

“The experience is exhausting and confusing; it consumes your energy.” (P6)

“It was difficult, stressful, and draining since we had much to prepare and revise.” (P7)

“It was intimidating, considering that it has the possibility that we have to publish our research internationally, with many people who are also targeting to publish.” (P8)

During the interview, the researchers observed that most participants have similar research publication experiences regarding their physical and mental well-being. Most of them experienced pressures and difficulties in publishing their research. The researcher presupposes that in aspiring to publish their research, they feel the stress and tension, and it causes fear in publishing their research. The researchers envisage that stress and tension caused them to feel exhausted over the entire semester. As mentioned by the participants:

“We felt pressured because there was an anticipation of rejection.” (P2)

“I feared because, of course, as a student researcher, we do not really know what should be included in our research.” (P4)

Lastly, the participants felt that doing research for publication is frustrating, tiring, and degrading. As Participants 4 and 5 averred:

“It is degrading and frustrating as there are so many comments and revisions. We started to feel apathetic.” (P4)

“We felt very anxious because, in the back of our minds, we were thinking that this is additional work for us.” (P5)

Discussion

This article sought to explore the experiences of preservice teachers as novice researchers in publishing their research outputs in a research journal. The first dimension is centered on the novice researchers' personal lives when they published their first research work. The research publication process can be challenging for everyone (Larson & Mulcahy, 2021), requiring more time and effort from the researchers. This explains the novice researchers' difficulty with time during the publication, which adds to the difference in academic workloads, schedules, and added personal circumstances. As such, familiar experiences revealed that postgraduate researchers' commitment issues with their personal lives and other responsibilities were hindrances that stopped them from constantly working on their papers, that includes internship and work-related responsibilities (Alvarez et al., 2014). Another challenge also reflects the difficulty of funding for the publication of the novice researchers' study (Duracinsky et al., 2017). This elucidates their experience of shouldering financial obligations during their publishing journey. The present findings suggest that similar challenges encompassing commitment issues, time constraints, and financial burdens are observable among novice researchers of the undergraduate preservice teachers in the Teacher Education Program.

On the other hand, the leveraging positive disposition dimension can be justified by the positive experiences of participants related to their research publication. The idea that novice researchers have had success publishing research that advances their study career is a blessing. In this study, one interesting finding is the excitement of novice researchers to publish one research in their field of specialization for the first time. This observation supports the assertion that publishing gives the author recognition within their professional community and a feeling of personal achievement (Atai et al., 2018; Radford et al., 2020). It is a feeling of accomplishment for novice researchers considering the intense pressure to publish and the limited knowledge of predatory journals that their research was published (Mercier et al., 2017). The increase in the relationships between novice researchers and publishing is of interest, which has a mutual exchange of leveraging dispositions, whether positive or negative (Li et al., 2019). This observation supports the exemplification that dispositional attitudes are a contrasting independent variable between novice researchers and the publishing itself, with the aptness to like or dislike stimuli (Hepler, 2015). Some novice researchers perceive leveraging positive dispositions as a positive and negative advancement keen on consequences through the mutual exchange of relationships between the novice researchers and their attitudes towards publishing.

As mentioned in the literature review, publishing research is a potential determining factor for novice researchers' career advancement. Research publication allows them to present their papers at an international conference. This finding is consistent with the observation that undergraduate researchers experienced professional benefits such as the opportunity to present at conferences after publishing their research (Matthews & Rosa, 2018). This implies that novice researchers have a higher hope of receiving career opportunities than researchers who have yet to publish their papers. Hence, publishing research in a professional journal can allow novice researchers to unlock a new chapter of their careers.

The third dimension suggests how novice researchers acknowledge their dependency on their research promoter, which is found to be significantly associated with meeting publishing standards as they hold unfamiliarity with the publication process. The third dimension focuses on how novice researchers were subject to their research promoter's guidance, supervision, and mentoring throughout the publication. Interestingly, it provides evidence for transactions and direct communications to the research publication made by the research promoter. Respecting the premise that novice researchers have inadequacy with any of the publication processes, particularly with submitting manuscripts,

undergoing peer-review, and revising, they are necessitated with guidance from their research promoter. It may be the case, therefore, that such significant finding reveals that part and parcel of the novice researchers' exigencies includes the help from experts on the publication or those who have significant experiences in publishing, which in this actuality are the research promoters (Fulton, 2018). Academic endeavors concluded by students often result in publishable outcomes. Thus, directing a student from schoolwork to a publishable manuscript is an ancillary effort involving research promoter guidance. Such effort brings to the need for heightened research promoter mentoring of student researchers and authors.

Moreover, research promoters serving as supervisors to students writing for a publication insinuates that the research promoter has significant experience and expertise in corresponding, conforming, and victoriously publishing their work (Fulton, 2018). These findings reveal something about the nature of submitting a manuscript to a research publication, in which a researcher needs to engage with peer reviewers, editors, and journal staff. Preparatory for submitting a journal, student researchers' manuscripts must constantly undergo their research promoter's review and approval so as when revising the manuscripts as advised by journal editors. Also, these findings further indicate that the supervision and guidance held by the research promoters are purposely intended to rear and boost the research writing standards and progressively drive ethical principles and practices associated with academic integrity into writing and publishing (Marsh & Campion, 2018).

Meeting the publication standard is the fourth dimension of the novice researcher's experiences. Standards ranging from the format, appropriateness, ethical consideration, and correctness of the research explain the strenuous work that the participants have experienced. As such, these standards are enforced to ensure that acts of falsification and plagiarism are not conducted during the process of revision (Pan, 2020). This also stresses the ethics of publication among research promoters and students to comply with all relevant policies and to present their study without inappropriate data manipulation (Patwardhan, 2015). Assessing the journal publication, whether legitimate or predatory, was also a highlighted concern. Predatory journals need more scholarly standards and practices for evaluating research and improving the quality and format of published work (Ferris & Winker, 2017). Although revising the study is considered the most challenging part for the participants, it is still essential for the study to be validated and formalized.

Of the difficulty of the work the participants exerted, rejection from the journal concerned the participants. As misconduct and deviation from the standards lead to rejection, other factors were addressed by the participants. They have assessed present factors such as poor writing quality and unrelated readership interest during the publication process (Reed et al., 2022). Although, most of them have expressed little to no agitation about having their research rejected. What was realized instead was a sense of difficulty in complying with what their promoter enforced on them. Their evident concern was not majorly the threat of rejection but the uncertainty of what the guidelines entail for publication. As novices who were dependent on their promoters, the structure, reliability, and content were the focus of the revision process. With all of these, the assurance for research publication was established for the participants.

Encountering poor physical and mental well-being is the final dimension of novice researchers' experiences. It primarily refers to physical and psychological health issues detrimental to researchers throughout the publication procedure. Caused by the highly valued peer-review process, many researchers widely regarded the importance of disseminating scholarly knowledge. Emotionally and psychologically demanding research affects researchers by requiring a massive amount of mental, emotional, or physical energy in doing research, potentially depleting the researcher's well-being. (Kumar & Cavallaro, 2018). Nevertheless, it is still considered an essential phase in the educational process. Thus far, physical and psychological health issues are a pressing concern for researchers during publication, and interventions must be provided to support their mental health and well-being. For novice researchers, a sensitive, emotionally charged study necessitates mental fortitude, emotional fortitude, and logistical help.

Little is known about the difficulties a novice researcher may face when conducting sensitive, emotionally charged research. It worsened when participants in such studies needed to figure out how to indicate the importance of a specific research topic. It has a negative advancement in terms of health, wealth, and happiness in publishing (Shackman et al., 2016). The findings show that novice researchers' concerns are related to excessive work, a lack of support from school management, and their agitated behavior. All these concerns are the primary impediments to novice researchers achieving their goals in publishing their research. Collectively, these factors indicate that the mental health of novice researchers is valuable but precarious. Indeed, research over the last decade has consistently found that researchers are more likely than the general population to experience high stress, exhaustion, and anxiety (Guthrie et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The current study was undertaken and designed to highlight the multidimensional and enriching nature of the journal publishing process, which encompasses both positive and negative experiences for novice researchers. This study focused on the entirety of the experiences of the preservice teachers as novice researchers in research journals. The experiences of preservice teachers in publishing their research outputs in research journals can be encapsulated by the acronym "FLAME," which represents the themes of (1) facing personal circumstances, (2) leveraging positive dispositions, (3) acknowledging dependency on research promoters, (4) meeting publishing standards, and (5) encountering poor physical and mental well-being. Although the current study is based on a small sample of participants, the FLAME model provides a deeper insight to the experiences of preservice teachers, implying that their positive and negative particularities compliment each other. These all-encompassing experiences provide a clear-cut picture of what publishing for the first time feels like for novice researchers, which contributes to existing knowledge on the sundry publication experiences of preservice teachers.

Contrary to previous literature, which strengthens the idea that publishing only highlights struggles, challenges, and barriers, the evidence from this study provides a new understanding that publishing also involves positive experiences. By shedding light on the experiences of preservice teachers, this study provides valuable insights into the challenges they face and the strategies they employ to navigate the publishing journey. The present study has been one of the first attempts to thoroughly examine the completeness and fullness of the experiences, particularly of preservice teachers as novice researchers in research journals. The identified themes can serve as a guide for novice researchers, offering support and guidance in their own research publication endeavors.

Furthermore, this research emphasizes the significance of mentorship and support from research promoters in facilitating successful publication. It is essential for academic institutions and mentors to provide adequate training, resources, and encouragement to help novice researchers overcome barriers and enhance their research publication skills. In conclusion, the publication process is not only a means of disseminating research findings but also a transformative and educational experience for novice researchers. By understanding and addressing the experiences faced by preservice teachers and other novice researchers, the academic community can work towards creating a more inclusive and supportive environment that fosters successful research publications.

Recommendations

The finding's compelling outcomes strongly recommend a greater course of action that can be used to develop mentorship programs and preparation for novice researchers to vitalize their research writing skills. Ensuring appropriate systems and support, it is correspondingly momentous for novice researchers to develop their independent research skills. The information procured can be utilized to develop targeted interventions for learning resources for competence elevation and publication effectiveness. Withal, further research on these questions would be a useful way of exploring the emotional and psychological demands of research on researchers and providing support to promote their well-being. Thus, a reasonable approach to tackle this affair is a need for an arable space for research promoters to provide a structured support system and guidance, such as insights on manuscript preparation, submission procedures, and ways to professionally address reviewers' comments. Essentially, this is to drive ethical principles and practices associated with academic integrity into writing and publishing.

Limitations

One area for improvement in this study is the small sample size, which may not represent all pre-service teachers as novice researchers. The study was conducted in a specific context and may not be generalizable to other contexts. The study also relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to bias. Conclusively, the study needed to explore the impact of publishing on the participants' academic and professional development beyond the publication process.

Ethics Statement

The Undergraduate Research and Innovation Coordinator (UGRIC) and the dean of the School of Teacher Education and Liberal Arts (STELA) at Saint Louis University evaluated and authorized the research with human participants. A written consent form was completed by every participant before involvement in the research.

Authorship Contribution Statement

Catama: Conceptualization, design, validation and data curation, supervision, final approval, and critical revision of the manuscript. Garcia: Conceptualization, writing, acquisition of data, validation and data curation, reviewing, and editing. Balinhawang: Conceptualization, writing, analysis and interpretation, validation and data curation, technical support, reviewing, and editing. Bobadilla: Conceptualization, writing, acquisition of data, validation and data curation, reviewing, and editing. Chiok: Conceptualization, writing, acquisition of data, validation and data curation, material support, reviewing, and editing. Diwata: Conceptualization, writing, analysis and interpretation, validation and data curation, reviewing, and editing. Ferrer: Conceptualization, writing, analysis and interpretation, validation and data curation,

reviewing, and editing. Gacelan: Conceptualization, writing, acquisition of data, validation and data curation, reviewing, and editing. Carreon: Conceptualization, writing, analysis and interpretation, validation and data curation, material support, reviewing, and editing.

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